

Replication of "The Impact of the WWI Agricultural Boom and Bust on Female Opportunity Cost and Fertility"

Description:

This replication package includes all datasets and code to replicate "The Impact of the WWI Agricultural Boom and Bust on Female Opportunity Cost and Fertility."

The replication package includes 20 folders.

19/20 of the folders contain raw data and code to replicate specific results in the paper.

1/20 folder "**non-proprietary datasets**", provides each of the 51 unique datasets in a comma-separated value format. Additionally, there are two subdirectories (1) shapefiles, which contains county and state boundary files (2) image files, contains 13 .tif files.

Below we provide instructions detailing which results are generated from the code and datasets contained within specific folders.

Data Summary: In the table below, we summarize all datasets used in the analysis. In this table, we summarize all datasets in their proprietary format, although copies in .csv format are included in the "non-proprietary datasets" folder.

Data.Name	Data.Files	Location(s)	Provided	Citation
1920 Complete Count, extract	1920_census.dta	Appendix Figure D1	YES	Ruggles, Steven, Sarah Flood, Ronald Goeken, Josiah Grover, Erin Meyer, Jose Pacas and Matthew Sobek. IPUMS USA: Version 10.0 [dataset]. Minneapolis, MN: IPUMS, 2020. https://doi.org/10.18128/D010.V10.0
1930 Complete Count, extract	1930_census.dta	Appendix Figure D1	YES	Ruggles, Steven, Sarah Flood, Ronald Goeken, Josiah Grover, Erin Meyer, Jose Pacas and Matthew Sobek. IPUMS USA: Version 10.0 [dataset]. Minneapolis, MN: IPUMS, 2020. https://doi.org/10.18128/D010.V10.0
1900 Census, County and State	02896-0020-Data.dta	Cohort Sample Replication, Mother panel replication, State Report Replication, Appendix Table A14	YES	Haines, Michael R., and Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research. Historical, Demographic, Economic, and Social Data: The United States, 1790-2002. Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research [distributor], 2010-05-21. https://doi.org/10.3886/ICPSR02896.v3
1910 Census, County and State	02896-0022-Data.dta	Cohort Sample Replication, Mother panel replication, State Report Replication,	YES	Haines, Michael R., and Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research. Historical, Demographic, Economic, and Social Data: The United States, 1790-2002. Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research [distributor], 2010-05-21. https://doi.org/10.3886/ICPSR02896.v3

		Appendix Table A14		
1930 Census I, County and State	02896-0026-Data.dta	Appendix Figure A2	YES	Haines, Michael R., and Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research. Historical, Demographic, Economic, and Social Data: The United States, 1790-2002. Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research [distributor], 2010-05-21. https://doi.org/10.3886/ICPSR02896.v3
1910 Agricultural Census	35206-0009-Data.dta	Cohort Sample Replication, Mother panel replication, State Report Replication, Figure 2, Appendix Figure A2, Appendix Figure A7, Appendix Table A14, Appendix Table B1	YES	Haines, Michael, Fishback, Price, and Rhode, Paul. United States Agriculture Data, 1840 - 2012. Ann Arbor, MI: Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research [distributor], 2018-08-20. https://doi.org/10.3886/ICPSR35206.v4
1920 Agricultural Census	35206-0010-Data.dta	Appendix Table A14	YES	Haines, Michael, Fishback, Price, and Rhode, Paul. United States Agriculture Data, 1840 - 2012. Ann Arbor, MI: Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research [distributor], 2018-08-20. https://doi.org/10.3886/ICPSR35206.v4

1925 Agricultural Census	35206-0012-Data.dta	Appendix Table A14	YES	Haines, Michael, Fishback, Price, and Rhode, Paul. United States Agriculture Data, 1840 - 2012. Ann Arbor, MI: Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research [distributor], 2018- 08-20. https://doi.org/10.3886/ICPSR35206.v4
1930 Agricultural Census	35206-0013-Data.dta	Appendix Figure A2, Appendix Table A14	YES	Haines, Michael, Fishback, Price, and Rhode, Paul. United States Agriculture Data, 1840 - 2012. Ann Arbor, MI: Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research [distributor], 2018- 08-20. https://doi.org/10.3886/ICPSR35206.v4
Boll Weevil	Analysis_Master_1920.dta	Cohort Sample Replication, Mother panel replication, State Report Replication,	YES	Feigenbaum, J. J., Mazumder, S., & Smith, C. B. (2020). <i>When Coercive Economies Fail: The Political Economy of the US South After the Boll Weevil</i> (No. w27161).
County-Level Birth Panel	births.county.panel.dta	State Report Replication	YES	Coded by the authors from state health reports as outlined in Appendix Table A3.
Complete Count Census, appended	census_1900to1930.dta	Cohort Sample Replication	YES	Ruggles, Steven, Sarah Flood, Ronald Goeken, Josiah Grover, Erin Meyer, Jose Pacas and Matthew Sobek. IPUMS USA: Version 10.0 [dataset]. Minneapolis, MN: IPUMS, 2020. https://doi.org/10.18128/D010.V10.0
Census Regions	census_region.dta	State Report Replication,	YES	US Census Bureau. Original excel located at https://www2.census.gov/programs- surveys/popest/geographies/2017/state-geocodes- v2017.xlsx

County Health Organizations	CHOvelasco.dta	Cohort Sample Replication, Mother panel replication, State Report Replication,	YES	Provided by Lauren Hoehn-Velasco, used in Hoehn-Velasco, L. (2019). The Long-term Impact of Preventative Public Health Programs. Working paper. http://www.laurenhoehnvelasco.com/research/
County Fips Codes	county_fips.xlsx	Cohort Sample Replication, Mother Panel Replication, State Report Replication	YES	https://transition.fcc.gov/oet/info/maps/census/fips/fips.txt
Complete Count Census, extract	Complete_count_1930.dta	Mother Panel Replication	YES	Ruggles, Steven, Sarah Flood, Ronald Goeken, Josiah Grover, Erin Meyer, Jose Pacas and Matthew Sobek. IPUMS USA: Version 10.0 [dataset]. Minneapolis, MN: IPUMS, 2020. https://doi.org/10.18128/D010.V10.0
WWI Draft	county_inductions.dta	Cohort Sample Replication	YES	Coded by the authors from: Final Report of the Provost Marshall General to the Secretary of War. (1920). U.S. Government Printing Office. Washington, D.C.
County Population	county_pop.dta	Cohort Sample Replication,	YES	Decennial Census County Population data 1900-1910. NBER https://www.nber.org/research/data/census-us-decennial-county-population-data-1900-1990

		Mother Panel Replication		
1900 County Boundaries in 1910	countyBoundary1900_1910.xls	Cohort Sample Replication	YES	Decade specific county boundaries constructed from Atlas of Historical County Boundaries https://digital.newberry.org/ahcb/downloads/index.html Decade Specific boundaries then overlaid in ArcGIS using the intersect command.
1920 County Boundaries in 1910	countyBoundary1920_1910.xls	Cohort Sample Replication	YES	Decade specific county boundaries constructed from Atlas of Historical County Boundaries https://digital.newberry.org/ahcb/downloads/index.html Decade Specific boundaries then overlaid in ArcGIS using the intersect command.
1930 County Boundaries in 1910	countyBoundary1930_1910.xls	Cohort Sample Replication, Mother Panel Replication, State Report Replication, Appendix Figure A7, Appendix Table B1	YES	Decade specific county boundaries constructed from Atlas of Historical County Boundaries https://digital.newberry.org/ahcb/downloads/index.html Decade Specific boundaries then overlaid in ArcGIS using the intersect command.
Predicted Crop Yields	crop_yields.xls, crop_yields.dta	Appendix Table B1	YES	Generated from running code in folder “Appendix Table B1”
Observed Crop Index	cropIndexMap04.12.21.xls	Figure 4	YES	Constructed from Index.do
Predicted Crop Shares	cropShares.dta	Appendix Table B1	YES	Generated from running code in folder “Appendix Table B1”

County Code Crosswalks	crosswalk.dta	Cohort Sample Replication, Mother Panel Replication, State Report Replication, Appendix Table A14	YES	Author Generated
County Level Mortality	death_panel.dta	Cohort Sample Replication, Mother Panel Replication, State Report Replication	YES	Data hand collected from state vital statistics reports as described in the text.
Spanish Flu Measure	excess_mortality_1918_update.csv	Appendix Figure A5	YES	Data hand collected from state vital statistics reports as described in the text.
Female Labor Force Participation	female_lfp_1900.dta	State Report Replication,	YES	Ruggles, Steven, Sarah Flood, Ronald Goeken, Josiah Grover, Erin Meyer, Jose Pacas and Matthew Sobek. IPUMS USA: Version 10.0 [dataset]. Minneapolis, MN: IPUMS, 2020. https://doi.org/10.18128/D010.V10.0
Raw Birth and Income Trends	fertility and income trends.xlsx	Figure 1, Appendix Figure A1	YES	<i>National Center for Health Statistics. (2017). NCHS – Births and General Fertility Rates. National Center for Health Statistics, National Vital Statistics System. Date accessed: 06/01/2020. https://data.cdc.gov/NCHS/NCHS-Births-and-General-Fertility-Rates-United-Sta/e6fc-ccez</i>

Coefficients	Figure4_cohort_sample_data	Appendix Figure A4	YES	Generated from Cohort Analysis and Mother Panel Analysis
Coefficients	Figure4_mother_panel_data	Appendix Figure A4	YES	Generated from Cohort Analysis and Mother Panel Analysis
BLS City Food Prices 1913-1928	foodPrices_1913_1928	Appendix Figure A7	YES	United States Department of Labor. Bureau of Labor Statistics. Bulletin No. 495. Retail Prices 1890 to 1928. United States Government Printing Office. Washington, D.C. 1929.
Rosenwald Schools	Infantmort_rose.dta	Cohort Sample Replication, Mother Panel Replication, State Report Replication	YES	Aaronson, D., Lange, F., & Mazumder, B. (2014). Fertility transitions along the extensive and intensive margins. <i>American Economic Review</i> , 104(11), 3701-24.
Malaria Mortality, 1937	malaria_death_1937.csv	Cohort Sample Replication, Mother Panel Replication, State Report Replication, Appendix Figure A6	YES	Kitchens, C. (2013). The effects of the Works Progress Administration's anti-malaria programs in Georgia 1932–1947. <i>Explorations in Economic History</i> , 50(4), 567-581. Supplemented with data entered by authors from state health reports.
	New_York_births_pre_correction	Appendix Figure D1	YES	Eriksson, K., Niemesh, G. T., & Thomasson, M. (2018). Revising infant mortality rates for the early twentieth century United States. <i>Demography</i> , 55(6), 2001-2024.

Pennsylvania Female Wages	PA_wages (note: in the proprietary free folder, we have separate files for males and females)	Figure 3	YES	Encoded by Authors from Pennsylvania crop report volumes 1908-1922. https://hdl.handle.net/2027/uiug.30112064299545 https://hdl.handle.net/2027/coo.31924081987400
Population Variables, 1920	popVars_1920	State Report Replication,	YES	Haines 02896-0024.
Population Variables, 1930	popVars_1930	State Report Replication,	YES	Haines 02896-0027. f1544 variable is the sum of the other age-specific counts: f1519 + f2024 + f2529 + f3034 + f3544.
Predicted Crop Index – IV	Predicted_Index	Appendix Table B1	YES	Generated from running code in folder “Appendix Table B1”
Prohibition Variables	Prohibition_values	Cohort Sample Replication, Mother Panel Replication, State Report Replication	YES	Encoded by authors from the Anti-Saloon League year book, 1910-1919.
Rockefeller Hookworm Intervention	Rsc_hookworm_entry	Cohort Sample Replication, Mother Panel Replication, State Report Replication	YES	Encoded by the authors from the Rockefeller Sanitary Commission for the Eradication of Hookworm Disease, 1910-1914.

Compulsory Schooling	STATA Claudia 2	Cohort Sample Replication, Mother Panel Replication, State Report Replication	YES	Goldin, C., & Katz, L. F. (2008). Mass secondary schooling and the state: the role of state compulsion in the high school movement. In <i>Understanding long-run economic growth: Geography, institutions, and the knowledge economy</i> (pp. 275-310). University of Chicago Press
	State_report_ag_fertility	Figure 3, Appendix Figure D1, Appendix Table B1	YES	Generated from code in “State report replication files folder”
States in County Birth Sample	States_in_county_sample.csv	Appendix Figure A3		Author’s calculation
1930 Complete Count Census extract	usa_00022.dta	Cohort Sample Replication, Mother Panel Replication, State Report Replication, Appendix Table A14	YES	Ruggles, Steven, Sarah Flood, Ronald Goeken, Josiah Grover, Erin Meyer, Jose Pacas and Matthew Sobek. IPUMS USA: Version 10.0 [dataset]. Minneapolis, MN: IPUMS, 2020. https://doi.org/10.18128/D010.V10.0
1920 Complete Count Census extract	usa_00024.dta	Appendix Table A14	YES	Ruggles, Steven, Sarah Flood, Ronald Goeken, Josiah Grover, Erin Meyer, Jose Pacas and Matthew Sobek. IPUMS USA: Version 10.0 [dataset]. Minneapolis, MN: IPUMS, 2020. https://doi.org/10.18128/D010.V10.0

Annual Agricultural Wage Index	Usda.agWage.Index	Figure 3	YES	Encoded by Authors from: United States Department of Agriculture. (1931). Yearbook of Agriculture. U.S. Government Printing Office. Washington, D.C.
WWI Draft Inductions	Ww1.county.inductions	Cohort Sample Replication, Mother Panel Replication, State Report Replication	YES	Encoded by the authors from: Final Report of the Provost Marshall General to the Secretary of War. (1920). U.S. Government Printing Office. Washington, D.C.
Geographic Files				
State Boundaries	US_state_1930 (shapefiles)			
1910 County Boundaries	County_boundary_1910_project (shapefiles)			Decade specific county boundaries constructed from Atlas of Historical County Boundaries https://digital.newberry.org/ahcb/downloads/index.html
Raster Images				
UN FAO GAEZ	alfalfamed.tif	Appendix Table B1	YES	Fiszbein, Martin. "Agricultural Diversity, Structural Change, and Long-Run Development: Evidence from the United States." <i>American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics</i> 14, no. 2 (April 2022): 1–43. https://doi.org/10.1257/mac.20190285 . http://doi.org/10.3886/E119556V3
UN FAO GAEZ	barleymed.tif	Appendix Table B1	YES	Fiszbein, Martin. "Agricultural Diversity, Structural Change, and Long-Run Development: Evidence from the United States." <i>American Economic Journal:</i>

				<p><i>Macroeconomics</i> 14, no. 2 (April 2022): 1–43. https://doi.org/10.1257/mac.20190285.</p> <p>http://doi.org/10.3886/E119556V3</p>
UN FAO GAEZ	buckwheatmed.tif	Appendix Table B1	YES	<p>Fiszbein, Martin. “Agricultural Diversity, Structural Change, and Long-Run Development: Evidence from the United States.” <i>American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics</i> 14, no. 2 (April 2022): 1–43. https://doi.org/10.1257/mac.20190285.</p> <p>http://doi.org/10.3886/E119556V3</p>
UN FAO GAEZ	cornmed.tif	Appendix Table B1	YES	<p>Fiszbein, Martin. “Agricultural Diversity, Structural Change, and Long-Run Development: Evidence from the United States.” <i>American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics</i> 14, no. 2 (April 2022): 1–43. https://doi.org/10.1257/mac.20190285.</p> <p>http://doi.org/10.3886/E119556V3</p>
UN FAO GAEZ	cottonmed.tif	Appendix Table B1	YES	<p>Fiszbein, Martin. “Agricultural Diversity, Structural Change, and Long-Run Development: Evidence from the United States.” <i>American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics</i> 14, no. 2 (April 2022): 1–43. https://doi.org/10.1257/mac.20190285.</p> <p>http://doi.org/10.3886/E119556V3</p>
UN FAO GAEZ	flaxmed.tif	Appendix Table B1	YES	<p>Fiszbein, Martin. “Agricultural Diversity, Structural Change, and Long-Run Development: Evidence from the United States.” <i>American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics</i> 14, no. 2 (April 2022): 1–43. https://doi.org/10.1257/mac.20190285.</p> <p>http://doi.org/10.3886/E119556V3</p>
UN FAO GAEZ	oatsmed.tif	Appendix Table B1	YES	<p>Fiszbein, Martin. “Agricultural Diversity, Structural Change, and Long-Run Development: Evidence from the United States.” <i>American Economic Journal:</i></p>

				<p><i>Macroeconomics</i> 14, no. 2 (April 2022): 1–43. https://doi.org/10.1257/mac.20190285.</p> <p>http://doi.org/10.3886/E119556V3</p>
UN FAO GAEZ	pasturegrassesmed.tif	Appendix Table B1	YES	<p>Fiszbein, Martin. “Agricultural Diversity, Structural Change, and Long-Run Development: Evidence from the United States.” <i>American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics</i> 14, no. 2 (April 2022): 1–43. https://doi.org/10.1257/mac.20190285.</p> <p>http://doi.org/10.3886/E119556V3</p>
UN FAO GAEZ	potatomed.tif	Appendix Table B1	YES	<p>Fiszbein, Martin. “Agricultural Diversity, Structural Change, and Long-Run Development: Evidence from the United States.” <i>American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics</i> 14, no. 2 (April 2022): 1–43. https://doi.org/10.1257/mac.20190285.</p> <p>http://doi.org/10.3886/E119556V3</p>
UN FAO GAEZ	ryemed.tif	Appendix Table B1	YES	<p>Fiszbein, Martin. “Agricultural Diversity, Structural Change, and Long-Run Development: Evidence from the United States.” <i>American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics</i> 14, no. 2 (April 2022): 1–43. https://doi.org/10.1257/mac.20190285.</p> <p>http://doi.org/10.3886/E119556V3</p>
UN FAO GAEZ	sweetpotatomed.tif	Appendix Table B1	YES	<p>Fiszbein, Martin. “Agricultural Diversity, Structural Change, and Long-Run Development: Evidence from the United States.” <i>American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics</i> 14, no. 2 (April 2022): 1–43. https://doi.org/10.1257/mac.20190285.</p> <p>http://doi.org/10.3886/E119556V3</p>
UN FAO GAEZ	tobaccomed.tif	Appendix Table B1	YES	<p>Fiszbein, Martin. “Agricultural Diversity, Structural Change, and Long-Run Development: Evidence from the United States.” <i>American Economic Journal:</i></p>

				<p><i>Macroeconomics</i> 14, no. 2 (April 2022): 1–43. https://doi.org/10.1257/mac.20190285.</p> <p>http://doi.org/10.3886/E119556V3</p>
UN FAO GAEZ	wheatmed.tif	Appendix Table B1	YES	<p>Fiszbein, Martin. “Agricultural Diversity, Structural Change, and Long-Run Development: Evidence from the United States.” <i>American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics</i> 14, no. 2 (April 2022): 1–43. https://doi.org/10.1257/mac.20190285.</p> <p>http://doi.org/10.3886/E119556V3</p>

Data Availability:

To access specific raw datasets, individuals will require accounts at ICPSR.org, usa.ipums.org, and be members of the American Economic Association to access datasets from author replication files.

All data used in this project have been made available via the replication package.

Packages and Libraries:

The analysis in this package utilized the following software and versions:

Esri ArcMap 10.7.1

IDLE (Python GUI for Python version 2.7.17) – Esri ArcMap license is required to use the arcpy library

Stata 15 SE

Stata 13 MP

Stata packages to install. Available via SSC install: “reghdfe”, “ivreghdfe”, “outreg2”, “binscatter”, “fmlogit”, “lgraph”

Instructions and Output:

Below we detail the order to run the code in each subfolder within the “3-replication” directory.

1. Open the “state report replication files” folder. This folder generates results reported in

- Table 1
- Figure 6
- Figure 7
- Table A2
- Table A5
- Table A6
- Table A7
- Table A8, Panel A
- Table A11, Column 3
- Table A13, Panel A

Runtime: This folder and code will take approximately 15 minutes to execute.

Input Datafiles: Ensure that the following data files are located in the folder.

- "countyBoundary1930_1910.xls". Information on how county boundaries shifted. Necessary to correctly assign births and covariates.
- "35206-0009-Data.dta". Agricultural data (Haines, Fishback, & Rhode; ICPSR)
- "Index.do". Stata code that generates the crop price index.
- "births.county.panel.xlsx". County-level birth records from state health reports and Birth Registration Area data.
- "02896-0022-Data.dta". Baseline county information (Haines, ICPSR)
- "CHOvalesco.dta". County Health Organization data from Valesco.
- "crosswalk.dta". The crosswalk between the ICP codes and county FIPS codes.
- "rsc_hookworm_entry.xlsx". Hookworm eradication data. (Bleakley & Lange)
- "infantmort_rose.dta". Rosenwald School initiatives (Aaronson & Lange - AER website)
- "02896-0020-Data.dta". Manufacturing data (Haines, ICPSR)
- "usa_00022.dta". 1910 Complete Count Census data to generate female labor force variables (Ref: IPUMS)
- "ww1.county.inductions.xlsx". World War I induction data.
- "county_fips.xlsx". Used to facilitate induction data merge.
- "malaria_death_1937.xlsx". Malaria deaths (Kitchens)
- "STATA Claudia 2.dta". Compulsory schooling data (Claudia Goldin's website)
- "deaths_panel.dta". Death statistics from state records.
- "Analysis_Master_1920.xlsx". Boll weevil data (Feigenbaum)
- "census_region.dta". Coding for Census regions.
- "prohibition_values.xlsx". Anti-Saloon League Yearbooks
- "popVars_1920.dta" Census data for 1920. Used for interpolation.
- "popVars_1930.dta" Census data for 1930. Used for interpolation.
- "female_lfp_1900.dta" 1900 Census complete count data restricted to variables used in labor force participation check.

Executable Files: Whenever you run a do-file, ensure that the path directory is updated. Ensure that the following data files are located in the folder.

- "Index.do"
- "build_state_report_dataset.do"
- "state_report_regressions_figures.do"

Order to Run Executable Files:

- (1) **"build_state_report_dataset.do"**
 - a. This file generates output **"state_report_ag_fertility.dta"** which will be used in the next step, and in the replication of Appendix B, Figure 3 and Appendix D (be sure to place a copy of **state_report_ag_fertility.dta** into their respective folders.)
- (2) **"state_report_regressions_figures.do"** file. Make sure the "state_report_ag_fertility.dta" that you generated above is in the same folder.

Output Files:

- "state_report_ag_fertility.dta"
- "table1_results.xls"
- "figure6.gph"
- "figure7.gph"
- "tableA2_results.txt"
- "tableA5_results.xls"
- "tableA6_results.xls"
- "tableA7_results.xls"
- "tableA8_panelA_results.xls"
- "tableA11_col3_results.xls"
- "tableA13_panelA_results.xls"

2. Open the "**Mother panel replication files**" subfolder. This folder generates results reported in
 - Figure 5
 - Table 2
 - Figure A4 – (mother panel results. The "figureA4_mother_data.dta" file produced can be combined with the datafile created in the cohort sample subfolder to accurately reproduce what is in the paper once both sets of regressions are completed. To do so, simply combine the two Figure A4 datasets and use the same two-way plot selections. See Appendix Figure A4 subfolder See Appendix Figure A4 subfolder instructions below.
 - Table A3
 - Table A8, Panel B
 - Table A9, Panel A
 - Table A10, Columns 1 and 2
 - Table A12

Runtime: We used 64GB of RAM and a 12-core processor to perform the analysis, which took about 10 days on our system

Input Datafiles:

Whenever you run a do-file, ensure that the path directory is updated. Ensure that the following data files are located in the folder.

- "complete_count1930.dta". The 1930 Census complete count. (Ref: IPUMS)
- "crosswalk.dta". The crosswalk between the ICP codes and county FIPS codes.
- "35206-0009-Data.dta". Agricultural data (Haines, Fishback, & Rhode; ICPSR)
- "countyBoundary1930_1910.xls". Information on how county boundaries shifted. Necessary to correctly assign births and covariates.
- "02896-0022-Data.dta". Baseline county information (Haines, ICPSR)
- "02896-0020-Data.dta". Manufacturing data (Haines, ICPSR)
- "usa_00022.dta". 1910 Complete Count Census data to generate female labor force participation variable (Ref: IPUMS)
- "ww1.county.inductions.xlsx". World War I induction data.
- "county_fips.xlsx". Used to facilitate induction data merge.
- "county_pop". County population data from Census used to adjust induction rates.
- "CHOvalesco.dta". County Health Organization data from Valesco.
- "rsc_hookworm_entry.xlsx". Hookworm eradication data.
- "malaria_death_1937.xlsx". Malaria deaths (Kitchens)
- "infantmort_rose.dta". Rosenwald School initiatives (Aaronson & Lange - AER website)
- "STATA Claudia 2.dta". Compulsory schooling data (Claudia Goldin's website)
- "Analysis_Master_1920.xlsx". Boll weevil data (Feigenbaum)
- "prohibition_values.xlsx". Anti-Saloon League Yearbooks
- "deaths_panel.dta". Death statistics from state records.

Executable Files:

- "Index.do". Stata code that generates our the crop price index.
- "build_mother_panel.do". Code that builds the panel.
- "build_mother_panel_controls.do". Code that cleans and generates all control variables.
- "mother_panel_regressions_figures.do". Code that performs the regression analysis and generates figures.

Order to Run Executable Files:

- (1) "build_mother_panel_controls.do", this will generate "mother_panel_controls.dta" as well as all of the supplemental data files for robustness checks: "county_inductions.dta", "CHO_panel.dta", "hookworm.dta", "malaria_death_1937.dta", "rosenwald.dta", "compulsory.dta", "bollweevil.dta", "prohibition.dta", "exc_mort.dta". These files are called during subsequent steps.
- (2) "build_mother_panel.do", this will generate "mother_panel.dta"
- (3) "mother_panel_regressions_figures.do" generates the regression results and figures

Output Files:

- "mother_panel.dta"
- "figure5_panel_A_birthProb.gph"
- "figure5_panel_B_birthProb_farms.gph"
- "table2_results.xls"
- "tableA3_results.txt"
- "figureA4_mother_panel.gph"
- "figureA4_mother_panel_data.dta"
- "tableA8_panelB_results.xls"
- "tableA9_panelA_results.xls"
- "tableA10_colland2_results.xls"
- "tableA12_results.xls"

3. Open the "**Cohort sample replication files**" subfolder. This folder generates results reported in
 - Table 3
 - Table 4
 - Table A4
 - Figure A4 - cohort sample results (cross-section). The "figureA4_cohort_sample_data.dta" file produced can be combined with the datafile created in the "mother panel" subfolder to accurately reproduce what is in the paper once both sets of regressions are completed. To do so, simply combine the two Figure A4 datasets and use the same two-way plot selections. See Appendix Figure A4 subfolder instructions below.
 - Table A8, Panels C and D
 - Table A9, Panels B and C
 - Table A10, Columns 3 through 6
 - Table A11, Columns 1, 2, 4, and 5
 - Table A13, Panels B and C

Runtime: We used 64GB of RAM and a 12-core processor to perform the analysis, which took about a week on our system

Input Datafiles:

- "census_1900to1930.dta". The Census complete count for years 1900-1930. (Ref: IPUMS)
- "crosswalk.dta". The crosswalk between the ICP codes and county FIPS codes.
- "35206-0009-Data.dta". Agricultural data (Haines, Fishback, & Rhode; ICPSR)
- "countyBoundary1930_1910.xls". Information on how county boundaries shifted. Necessary to correctly assign births and covariates.
- "countyBoundary1920_1910.xls". Same as above but for adjustments between 1910 and 1920.
- "countyBoundary1900_1910.xls". Same as above but for adjustments between 1900 and 1910.
- "02896-0022-Data.dta". Baseline county information (Haines, ICPSR)
- "02896-0020-Data.dta". Manufacturing data (Haines, ICPSR)
- "usa_00022.dta". 1910 Complete Count Census data to generate female labor force participation variable (Ref: IPUMS)
- "ww1.county.inductions.xlsx". World War I induction data.
- "county_fips.xlsx". Used to facilitate induction data merge.
- "county_pop". County population data from Census used to adjust induction rates.
- "CHOvalesco.dta". County Health Organization data from Valesco.
- "rsc_hookworm_entry.xlsx". Hookwork eradication data.
- "malaria_death_1937.xlsx". Malaria deaths (Kitchens)
- "infantmort_rose.dta". Rosenwald School initiatives (Aaronson & Lange - AER website)
- "STATA Claudia 2.dta". Compulsory schooling data (Claudia Goldin's website)
- "Analysis_Master_1920.xlsx". Boll weevil data (Feigenbaum)
- "prohibition_values.xlsx". Anti-Saloon League Yearbooks
- "deaths_panel.dta". Death statistics from state records.

Executable Files:

- "Index.do". Stata code that generates our the crop price index.
- "build_cohort_sample.do". Code that builds the cohort sample dataset.
- "build_cohort_sample_controls.do". Code that cleans and generates all control variables.
- "cohort_sample_regressions_figures.do". Code that performs the regression analysis and generates figures.

Order to Run Executable Files:

- (1) "build_cohort_sample_controls.do" generates "cohort_sample_controls.dta"
- (2) "build_cohort_sample.do" generates "cohort_sample.dta"
- (3) "cohort_sample_regressions_figures.do"

Output Files:

- "cohort_sample.dta"
- "table3_results.xls"
- "table4_results.xls"
- "tableA4_results.txt"
- "figureA4_cohort_sample_data.dta"
- "figureA4_cohort_sample.gph"
- "tableA8_panelCD_results.xls"
- "tableA9_panelBC_results.xls"
- "tableA10_col3to6_results.xls"
- "tableA11_col1245_results.xls"
- "tableA13_panelBC_results.xls"

4. Open the **“Figure 1 – US Fertility Rate”** subfolder. This folder generates results reported in:
 - Figure 1

Runtime: Under 1 minute.

Input Datafiles:

- “fertility and income trends.xlsx”

Executable Files:

- “figure1.do”

Order to Run Executable Files:

- (1) “figure1.do”

Output Files:

- “birth_trends_full.png”

5. Open the “**Figure 2 – Crop Price Variation 1900-1930**” subfolder. This folder generates results reported in:
 - Figure 2

Runtime: Under 1 minute.

Input Datafiles:

- “35206-0009-Data.dta”

Executable Files:

- “figure2.do”. Note that this do file calls the “Index.do” that should also be in the same subfolder.

Order to Run Executable Files:

- (1) “figure2.do”

Output Files:

- “figure2_individual_crop_price_trends.png”

6. Open the “**Figure 3 – Agricultural Price Index and Wage Index 1910-1930**” subfolder. This folder generates results reported in:
 - Figure 3, Panel A
 - Figure 3, Panel B

Runtime: Under 1 minute.

Input Datafiles:

- “PA_wages.xlsx”
- “usda.agWage.Index.xlsx”
- “state_report_ag_fertility.dta”, must be copied from the “State report replication files” subfolder after that step is completed (above)

Executable Files:

- “figure3.do”

Order to Run Executable Files:

(2) “figure3.do”

Output Files:

- “figure3_panel_A_index_vs_wages_panel.png”
- “figure3_panel_B_wages_PA.png”

7. Open the “**Figure 4 – Spatial Variation in Agricultural Index**” subfolder. This folder generates results reported in:
 - Figure 4, Panel A
 - Figure 4, Panel B
 - Figure 4, Panel C
 - Figure 4, Panel D
 - Figure 4 legend

Runtime: Under 5 minutes.

Input Datafiles:

- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shx”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.dbf”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.prj”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.sbn”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.sbx”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shp”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shp.mxl”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shx”
- countyBoundary_1910_project.cpg”
- cropIndexMap04.12.21.csv

Executable Files:

"index_maps.mxd"

Order (Instructions) to Run Executable Files:

- (1) Open ArcGIS .mxd file "index_maps.mxd". This map file will contain two objects, countyBoundary_1910_project.shp and cropIndexMap04.12.21.csv. These files have been joined using fips_1 in countyBoundary_1910_project and fipsco in cropIndexMap04.12.21.csv, keeping only observations with a match.

Repeat steps (a)-(e), replacing value with : index1914, index1919, index1924, index1929

- a. Right click on countyBoundary_1910_1 and select properties.
- b. click on quantities--> graduated colors.
- c. in the fields, ensure the following are selected
 - value: index1914
 - normalization: none
 - classes: 23
 - range: 1, 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.4, ... 3, 3.1, 3.2
- d. click Okay.
- e. File--> Export Map (note: we used the naming convention index_year.png)
- f. to make the legend, click Layout View. Then, click on Insert (toolbar)--> Legend. Select countyBounary_1910_project and move to be a legend item, set the number of columns = 8, then click next, then Finish. Right click on the Legend and click properties. Click the General tab, rename Legend “Agricultural Price Index”, click the Items Tab, then click Style click on Style, select

“Horizontal Single Symbol Label Only, click Okay, click okay again. Copy the legend and paste in paint, save as “figure4_index.png”

Output Files:

- “index_14.png”
- “index_19.png”
- “index_24.png”
- “index_29.png”
- “figure4_index.png”

8. Open the "**Appendix Figure A1 – US Fertility and Crude Birth Rate, 1910-1930**" subfolder. This folder generates results reported in
 - Appendix Figure A1

Runtime: Under 1 minute.

Input Datafiles:

- “fertility and income trends.xlsx”

Executable Files:

- “appendix_figure_A1.do”

Order to Run Executable Files:

- (3) “appendix_figure_A1.do”

Output Files:

- “figureA1_birth_trends.png”

9. Open the "**Appendix Figure A2 – Correlation between 1919 Retail Sales and Agricultural Index**" subfolder. This folder generates results reported in
 - Appendix Figure A2

Runtime: Under 1 minute.

Input Datafiles:

- "02896-0026-Data.dta"
- "35206-0009-Data.dta"
- "35206-0013-Data.dta"

Executable Files:

- "figure_A2.do"

Order to Run Executable Files:

- (1) "figure_A2.do"

Output Files:

- "figure_A2.png"

10. Open the “**Appendix Figure A3 – States in County Birth Sample**” subfolder. This folder generates results reported in

- Appendix Figure A3

Runtime: Under 5 minutes.

Input Datafiles:

- “states_in_county_sample.csv”
- “US_state_1930.dbf”
- “US_state_1930.prj”
- “US_state_1930.sbn”
- “US_state_1930.sbx”
- “US_state_1930.shp”
- “US_state_1930.shp.mxl”
- “US_state_1930.shx”

Executable Files:

“appendix figure A3 – states in county sample.mdx”

Order to Run Executable Files:

Open ArcGIS .mxd file "appendix figure A3 - states in county sample "

This map file will contain two objects, (1)US_state_1930.shp (2) states_in_county_sample.csv

The files, US_state_1930.shp and states_in_county_sample.csv have been joined using STATENAME in both files. In the states_in_county_sample.csv file, the variable in_sample = 0 if the data are not in any sample, in_sample = 1 if the data are in our primary sample, and in_sample = 2 if we use the data from these states in robustness checks.

To generate the map

1. Right click on US_state_1930.shp and select properties.
2. click on quantities--> graduated colors.
3. in the fields, ensure the following are selected

value: in_sample

normalization: none

classes: 3

range: 0,1,2

4. click Okay.

5. File--> Export Map (figure A3.png)

Output Files:

- “figure A3.png”

11. Open the “**Appendix Figure A4 – Robustness to Potential Confounds**” subfolder. This folder generates results reported in

- Appendix Figure A4

Runtime: under 1 minute

Input Datafiles:

- “figurea4_mother_panel_data.dta” Note: this file is created during the “Mother panel replication files” steps above. Place a copy of this file in the Appendix Figure A4 subfolder before continuing.
- “figurea4_cohort_sample_data.dta” Note: this file is created during the “Cohort sample replication files” steps above. Place a copy of this file in the Appendix Figure A4 subfolder before continuing.

Executable Files:

- “figure_A4.do”

Order to Run Executable Files:

(1) “figure_A4.do”

Output Files:

- figureA4.png

12. Open the “**Appendix Figure A5 – County-Level Excess Mortality 1918-1920, Spanish Influenza.**”

The figure generates results reported in

- Appendix Figure A5

Runtime: under 5 minutes

Input Datafiles:

- “US_state_1930.dbf”
- “US_state_1930.prj”
- “US_state_1930.sbn”
- “US_state_1930.sbx”
- “US_state_1930.shp”
- “US_state_1930.shp.mxl”
- “US_state_1930.shx”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shx”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.dbf”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.prj”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.sbn”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.sbx”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shp”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shp.mxl”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shx”
- countyBoundary_1910_project.cpg”
- “excess_mortality_1918_update.csv”

Executable Files:

“appendix figure A5 – Spanish flu excess mortality.mxd

Order to Run Executable Files:

Open ArcGIS .mxd file " appendix figure A5 - spanish flu excess mortality.mxd"

This map file will contain three objects, (1)US_state_1930.shp (2) countyBoundary_1910_project.shp and (3) excess_mortality_1918_update.csv

The files, countyBoundary_1910_project.shp and excess_mortality_1918_update.csv have been joined using fips_1 in countyBoundary_1910_project and FIPS in excess_mortality_1918_update.csv, keeping only observations with a match.

To generate the map

1. Right click on countyBoundary_1910_1 and select properties..
2. click on quantities--> graduated colors.
3. in the fields, ensure the following are selected

value: exc_mort

normalization: none

classes: 20

range: <0, .05, .1, .15, ... , .85, .9, .95, >.95

4. click Okay.

5. File--> Export Map (appendix figure A5 – spanish flu excess mortality.png”)

Output Files:

“appendix figure A5 – spanish flu excess mortality.png”

13. Open the “**Appendix Figure A6 – 1937 Malaria Mortality**” subfolder. This folder generates results reported in

- Appendix Figure A6

Runtime: under 5 minutes

Input Datafiles:

- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shx”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.dbf”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.prj”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.sbn”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.sbx”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shp”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shp.xml”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shx”
- countyBoundary_1910_project.cpg”
- malaria_death_1937.csv

Executable Files:

- “appendix figure A6 – malaria.mxd”

Order to Run Executable Files:

Open ArcGIS .mxd file "appendix figure A6 – malaria.mxd"

This map file will contain two objects, countyBoundary_1910_project.shp and malaria_death_1937.csv

These files have been joined using fips_1 in countyBoundary_1910_project and ICPSRFIP in malaria_death_1937.csv, keeping only observations with a match.

To generate the map

1. Right click on countyBoundary_1910_project and select properties.
2. click on quantities--> graduated colors.
3. in the fields, ensure the following are selected
 - value: malaria_death_rate_100k
 - normalization: none
 - classes: 11
 - range: 0, 3.3, 4.7, 7, 9.3, 11.4, 14.2, 18.2, 22.9, 35.2, 194
4. click Okay.
5. File--> Export Map (“appendix figure A6 – malaria.png”)

Output Files:

- “appendix figure A6 – malaria.png”

14. Open the “**Appendix Figure A7 – Correlation between food prices and agricultural index**” subfolder. This folder generates results reported in

- Appendix Figure A7

Runtime: under 1 minute

Input Datafiles:

- “35206-0009-Data.dta”
- “countyBoundary1930_1910.xls”
- “foodPrices_1913_1928.xlsx”

Executable Files:

- “figure_A7.do” Note that this calls the “Index.do” file that must be located in the same subfolder

Order to Run Executable Files:

(1) “figure_A7.do”

Output Files:

- figureA7.png

15. Open the “**Appendix Table A14 – Impact on Capital Share to Labor Share**” subfolder. This folder generates results reported in

- Appendix Table A14

Runtime: under 15 minutes

Input Datafiles:

- “02896-0020-Data.dta”
- “02896-0022-Data.dta”
- “35206-0009-Data.dta”
- “35206-0010-Data.dta”
- “35206-0012-Data.dta”
- “35206-0013-Data.dta”
- “countyBoundary1930_1910.xls”
- “crosswalk.dta”
- “usa_00022.dta”
- “usa_00024.dta”

Executable Files:

- “table_A14.do”

Order to Run Executable Files:

- (1) “table_A14.do”

Output Files:

- “tableA14_results.xls”

16. Open the “**Appendix Table B1 – Spatial-Temporal Variation in Predicted and Observed Index**” subfolder. This folder generates results reported in

- Appendix Figure B1 Panel B (a)
- Appendix Figure B1 Panel B (b)
- Appendix Figure B1 Panel B (c)
- Appendix Figure B1 Panel B (d)

Runtime: under 30 minutes

Input Datafiles:

- State_report_ag_fertility.dta (from previous output)
- cropShares.dta
- 35206-0009-Data.dta
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shx”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.dbf”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.prj”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.sbn”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.sbx”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shp”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shp.mxl”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shx”
- countyBoundary_1910_project.cpg”
- alfalfamed.tif
- barleymed.tif
- buckwheatmed.tif
- cornmed.tif
- cottonmed.tif
- flaxmed.tif
- oatsmed.tif
- pasturegrassmed.tif
- potatomed.tif
- ryemed.tif
- sweetpotatomed.tif
- tobaccomed.tif
- wheatmed.tif

Executable Files:

- buildCropSuit.py
- predicted_shares_suitability.do
- table_B1.do
-

Order to Run Executable Files:

- (1) Run “buildCropSuit.py” (Note: [1] be sure to change the directory in line 13 to your local machine directory. [2] it is important to run the python script with all files saved locally, as files stored remotely will encounter file locks due to ArcGIS's handling of files. Storing files in remote

locations like Dropbox will lead to unexpected errors.) This file will generate zonal statistics of each crop. It will generate the intermediate outputs “cropYields.gdb” and “cropYields.xls”

- (2) Run “predicted_shares_suitability.do”. This file will generate “cropShares.dta” and “predicted_Index.csv” which will be used in the IV analysis.
- (3) Ensure that the “state_report_ag_fertility.dta” dataset has already been generated within the "State report replication files" folder. Move a copy to this subfolder. Open the table_B1.do file and execute it.

Output Files:

- “cropYields.xls”
- “cropYields.gdb”
- “predicted_Index.csv (used in Appendix Figure B1)
- “cropShares.dta”
- “tableB1_results.xls”

Open the “**Appendix Figure B1 – Instrumental Variable Results**” subfolder. This folder generates results reported in

- Appendix Table B1

Runtime: under 5 minutes

Input Datafiles:

- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shx”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.dbf”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.prj”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.sbn”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.sbx”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shp”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shp.xml”
- “countyBoundary_1910_project.shx”
- countyBoundary_1910_project.cpg”
- “predicted_Index.csv (generated in Appendix Table B1)
-

Executable Files:

- “predicted_index_maps.mxd”

Order to Run Executable Files:

Open ArcGIS .mxd file "predicted_index_maps"

This map file will contain two objects, countyBoundary_1910_project.shp and predicted_Index.csv

These files have been joined using fips_1 in countyBoundary_1910_project and FIPS in predicted_Index.csv, keeping only observations with a match.

Repeat steps 1-4, replacing value with : index1914, index1919, index1924, index1929

1. Right click on countyBoundary_1910_1 and select properties.

2. click on quantities--> graduated colors.

3. in the fields, ensure the following are selected

value: index1914

normalization: none

classes: 23

range: 1, 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.4, ... 3, 3.1, 3.2

4. click Okay.

5. File--> Export Map

Note, the legend and figures in Panel B are copies of those reported in Figure 4 of the text.

Output Files:

- “predicted_index_1914.png”
- “predicted_index_1919.png”
- “predicted_index_1924.png”
- “predicted_index_1929.png”

17. Open the “**Appendix Figure D1 – Correlation of Births between State Health Reports and Complete Count**” subfolder. This folder generates results reported in

- Appendix Figure D1

Runtime: under 10 minutes

Input Datafiles:

- “1920_census.dta”
- “1930_census.dta”
- “New_York_births_pre_correction.xlsx”
- “state_report_ag_fertility.dta”, must be copied from the “State report replication files” subfolder after that step is completed (above)

Executable Files:

- “figure_D1.do”

Order to Run Executable Files:

(1) “figure_D1.do”

Output Files:

- comparison1920_orig.png
- comparison1920_fix.png
- comparison1930_orig.png
- comparison1930_fix.png